

Understanding sweetness of dry wines: First evidence of Astilbin isomers in red wines and quantitation in a one-century range of vintages

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Abstract

Astilbin (2*R*, 3*R*) was recently reported to contribute to wine sweetness [1]. As its aglycon contains two stereogenic centres, three other stereoisomers may be present: neoastilbin (2*S*, 3*R*), isoastilbin (2*R*, 3*S*), and neoastilbin (2*S*, 3*S*). These compounds have already been observed in natural products, but never in wine. This work aimed at assaying their presence for the first time in wines as well as their taste properties. The isomers were synthesised from astilbin and purified by semi-preparative HPLC. Sensory analysis highlighted the sweet taste of these stereoisomers whose intensity varied according to their configuration. Their content was assayed by developing a UHPLC-Q-Exactive quantification method. After validation, this method was applied to screen astilbin and isomers in various wines, especially in different vintages from the same estate. While young wines contained higher concentrations of astilbin than the old ones, the concentrations of the other isomers, mainly neoastilbin, were higher in the old wines, suggesting their formation over time.

Keywords: Sweetness, sensory analysis, taste, isomers, wines

Introduction

The gustatory balance of wines relies on sweetness, bitterness and sourness. In dry wines, sweetness does not result from the presence of residual sugars as in sweet wines, but is due to other non-volatile compounds. Natural sweet compounds released by oak wood [2, 3] or yeast lees [4] have been identified by taste-guided purification. Recently, such an approach allowed the isolation of two compounds from grapes that might contribute to the sweetness of dry wines: epi-DPA-G and astilbin [5, 6].

Astilbin, or (2*R*,3*R*)-3,3',4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavanon-3- α -L-rhamnopyranoside, is a dihydroflavonol rhamnoside found in many plants and plant-derived products, such as rhizoma of *Smilax glabra* [7], grape and wine [5,8,9]. The aglycon of astilbin is dihydroquercetin, also named taxifolin. It contains two stereogenic centres: carbons C-2 and C-3. Depending on the configuration of these carbons, astilbin (2*R*, 3*R*) has three other stereoisomers, i.e. neoastilbin (2*S*, 3*R*), isoastilbin (2*R*, 3*S*), and neoastilbin (2*S*, 3*S*), as shown in Figure 1 [10]. Astilbin was identified in wine for the first time by Trousdale and Singleton [8] within a concentration range of 0.10-2 mg/L. The sweet taste of astilbin has been recently described [5] and an LC-HRMS method has been developed to quantify it in dry wines [1]. However, the presence of astilbin isomers has never been reported in wine.

The present work investigated the presence of astilbin isomers in red wines. First, neoastilbin, isoastilbin, and neoastilbin were synthesised from astilbin and their sensory properties were assessed. Their presence was sought in commercial red wines by LC-HRMS targeted screening. A quantitative method was then applied to screen astilbin and its isomers in various commercial wines, especially in different vintages from the same estate, to analyse their evolution over time [11].

Experimental

Chemicals and commercial wines

Astilbin (LC-MS purity \geq 95 %) was isolated from vine stems by centrifugal partition chromatography and semi-preparative high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) according to the procedure described by Cretin [5]. Samples of 63 commercial red wines were used for isomers identification and quantitation. The wines were from various regions (39 from Bordeaux, 16 from Burgundy, 6 from Beaujolais, 1 from Roussillon and 1 from Germany) with vintages varying from 1918 to 2017. Among them, a series of different vintages from the same winery in Burgundy was analysed, i.e. 16 wines from 1918 to 2017.

Astilbin isomerisation

An aliquot of 340 mg of astilbin was dissolved in 300 mL of hydro-ethanolic solution (12 % v/v EtOH in ultrapure water) and pH was adjusted to 5 with formic acid. This value had been chosen after preliminary tests at various pHs. The mixture was heated at 60 °C for 7 days. After five liquid-liquid extractions with 50 mL of butanol saturated with water, the combined organic layers were evaporated to dryness, suspended in water and freeze-dried to obtain 323 mg of pale orange powder.

Purification by semi-preparative liquid chromatography

Semi-preparative HPLC analyses were performed using a Waters Prep 150 LC including a 2545 Quaternary Gradient Module, a 2489 UV/ Visible detector, and a 2424 ELSD detector (Waters, Guyancourt, France). An Atlantis T3 OBD prep column (19 × 250 mm, 5 µm, Waters, Guyancourt, France) was used. The mobile phase was a mixture of ultrapure water containing 0.1 % of formic acid (Eluent A) and acetonitrile with 0.1 % of formic acid (Eluent B). The flow rate was set to 20 mL/min. The gradient was 0 min, 10 % (B); 2.46 min, 10 % (B); 4.91 min, 20 % (B) 14.73 min, 20 % (B); 24.56 min, 25 % (B); 34.38 min, 50 % (B); 39.29, 98 % (B); 44.20 min, 98 % (B); 44.70, 10 % (B). Aliquots (around 40 mg) of powder were dissolved in 200 µL of methanol and in 200 µL of ultrapure water, 0.45 µm-filtered and successively introduced manually into the system. A total of 320 mg were injected. UV detection was carried out at 254 and 280 nm and chromatographic peaks were collected manually in tubes just after the detector. Samples obtained were pooled, evaporated *in vacuo* to remove acetonitrile, and freeze-dried to obtain white powders. Thus, 59 mg of astilbin, 29 mg of neoastilbin, 10.80 mg of isoastilbin and 25.40 mg of neoisoastilbin were obtained.

Sensory analysis

The sensory analysis took place in a specific room air-conditioned at 20 °C and equipped with individual booths. The compounds were dissolved at 5 mg/L in a non-oaked white wine (Bordeaux, 2013, 100 % Sauvignon blanc, 13 % vol. alc.). Samples were tasted in clear IAO wine glasses by five experts in wine-tasting (four women, one man, aged from 24 to 54 years old). The tasters were informed of the nature and risks of the present study and were asked for their written consent to participate. They were asked to describe the gustatory perception of each compound using the vocabulary of wine-tasting. Sweetness and acidity intensity were evaluated on a scale from 0 (not detectable) to 5 (strongly detectable) and compared to a blank solution. Even though the compounds were observed in wines, the panellists were advised not to swallow but to spit out the samples after tasting.

Liquid chromatography – High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (LC-HRMS)

Chromatographic separation was achieved using a Vanquish Flex system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Les Ulis, France) consisting in a binary pump, an autosampler and a heated column compartment. MS detection was performed using a Q-Exactive mass spectrometer equipped with a heated electrospray ionization (HESI II) probe (both from Thermo Fisher Scientific, Les Ulis, France). A C18 column is used, High Silica Strength (HSST3; 100 mm x 2.1 mm, 1.8 µm) from Waters. The flow rate was set at 400 µL/min. The injection volume was 5 µL and the eluents were (A) 0.1 % formic acid in water and (B) 0.1 % formic acid in acetonitrile. For the optimized gradient, eluent B varied as follows: 0 min, 10 %; 1 min, 20 %; 3 min, 20 %; 5 min, 25 %; 7 min, 50 %; 8 min, 98 %; 10 min, 98 %; 10.1 min, 10 %; 12 min, 10 %. The column and sample temperatures were 25 °C and 10 °C, respectively.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and Sensory Characterisation of Astilbin Stereoisomers

In a recent study, the analysis of a red wine by LC-HRMS revealed different signals in the extracted ion chromatogram (XIC) corresponding to *m/z* ions characteristic of the empirical formula of astilbin [1]. These results might suggest the presence of astilbin isomers in wine. Previous studies reported the isomerisation of astilbin and the mechanism of this reaction has been clearly established for taxifolin using quantum chemistry calculation and circular dichroism [11]. The same mechanism was proposed for the rhamnosyl derivatives [12]. The interconversion between astilbin (2R, 3R) and its stereoisomers involved a ring opening leading to a quinone methide. This compound can lead to neoisoastilbin (2S, 3R) by recyclization. The quinone methide can also epimerize by the formation of an α -hydroxychalcone to give isoastilbin (2R, 3S) and neoastilbin (2S, 3S) by recyclization (Figure 1). Preliminary tests guided the choice of a pH suited for isomerisation and avoiding hydrolysis of the glycoside moiety. Mild acidic conditions (pH 5) were subsequently chosen to stay close to the composition of wine. From a solution of pure astilbin, a mixture of four main compounds was obtained after 7 days at 60 °C. LC-HRMS confirmed that these compounds had the same *m/z* ions. After extraction with butan-1-ol, the reaction mixture was submitted to semi-preparative HPLC to purify the four isomers.

Figure 1: Interconversion of astilbin and its isomers neoastilbin, isoastilbin and neoisoastilbin.

The sensory properties of the four stereoisomers purified were then investigated. Five experts in wine-tasting evaluated the taste characteristics of a white non-oaked wine spiked individually with the compounds. They rated the intensity of sweetness, bitterness, and sourness on a scale from 0 to 5. The non-spiked wine used as a reference was evaluated as 1/5 for bitterness and sweetness, and 5/5 for acidity. An increase in sweetness was perceived for the modalities added with astilbin and isoastilbin (3/5 both). The taste of neoastilbin and neoisoastilbin was evaluated as sweeter (4/5 both). For all compounds, a decrease in acidity was also observed (3/5 for astilbin and neoisoastilbin, 4/5 for isoastilbin and neoastilbin). No impact on bitterness was detected. These results highlighted the sweetness of the four isomers, which confirmed and supplemented previous studies. Indeed, Kasai et al. [13] had extracted astilbin and its isomers from *Engelhardtia chrysolepis* leaves. Only neoastilbin was reported as sweet but the tasting conditions were not described [14]. The sweetness intensity of the isomers seemed to be influenced by their stereochemistry. Interestingly, for the sweetest compounds, neoisoastilbin and neoastilbin, the stereogenic centre C2 had an S absolute configuration.

Identification and quantitation of astilbin stereoisomers in red wines

A LC-HRMS method was developed to search for the presence of astilbin isomers in red wine. For each sample of wine analysed, extracted ion chromatograms (XIC) was built in a 5-ppm window around m/z 449.10681, which corresponded to the theoretical m/z of the deprotonated $[M-H]^-$ ion of astilbin. In most samples, five main peaks were observed in the XIC. Considering the mass measurement accuracy, four peaks suggested the presence of astilbin isomers. Spiking wine samples with standards led to a perfect co-elution and an increase in peak areas. To confirm this hypothesis, MS2 spectra were recorded for the five peaks. Their spectra were similar to that of astilbin and showed main fragment ions at m/z 303 and 285. These results confirmed the presence of neoastilbin, isoastilbin and neoisoastilbin in red wine. For the other peak, the MS2 spectra of $[M-H]^-$ ion showed different fragments at m/z 287 and 269, this compound might be dihydrokaempferol-3-O-glucoside. Analysis of pure standards would be necessary to identify its chemical structure unambiguously.

The method developed for targeted screening was also used for absolute quantitation of astilbin isomers in 63 commercial wines from different regions and different vintages. In all wines, astilbin was the most abundant stereoisomer. The average concentration of astilbin was 9.10 mg/L with a minimum value of 0.60 mg/L and a maximum value of 41.10 mg/L. Regarding isomers, the mean values of neoastilbin, neoisoastilbin and isoastilbin were 1.08, 0.70 and 1.03 mg/L respectively. The maximum concentrations of neoastilbin, neoisoastilbin and isoastilbin were 5.94, 2.73 and 4.45 mg/L respectively. All isomers were shown to increase the sweetness perception of a wine at 5 mg/L, so the quantitative results suggested the sensory potential of these flavanonols for some wines.

In the set of samples analysed in this work, there were a series of vintages from the same winery in Burgundy. Even if weather conditions and, to a lesser extent, winemaking techniques may differ from one vintage to another, such series could be useful for comparing the concentrations of astilbin stereoisomers in old or recent vintages. Figure 2 shows that young wines contained higher concentrations of astilbin than old ones, while the concentrations of the isomers, mainly neoastilbin, were higher in old wines. The difference in concentrations between astilbin and neoastilbin appeared to decrease over time. By plotting the vintage and the concentration, inverse correlations were observed for neoastilbin ($r^2 = 0.62$) and astilbin ($r^2 = 0.31$) (Figure 2). These results suggest that neoastilbin was formed over time, maybe through isomerisation of astilbin. The levels of isoastilbin and neoisoastilbin, albeit slightly higher in old wines, seemed less affected by the age of the wine.

Figure 2: Relationship between concentration of compounds and ageing in Pinot noir wines from a Burgundian winery.

Conclusion

This study reports the first identification of astilbin stereoisomers in wines. Isoastilbin, neoastilbin and neoisostilbin were synthesised to allow the study of their sensory properties. Their addition to a wine modified the taste balance by increasing the perceived sweetness, whose intensity varied according to the stereochemistry. Neoastilbin and neoisostilbin were the most active compounds. Their content was assayed by developing a UHPLC-Q-Exactive quantification method. After validation, this method was applied to screen astilbin and isomers in various wines, especially in different vintages from the same estate. While young wines contained higher concentrations of astilbin than the old ones, the concentrations of the other isomers, mainly neoastilbin, were higher in the old wines, suggesting their formation over time. These results highlight the contribution of astilbin isomers in wine sweetness. More generally, this study brings new insights to understand the chemical origin of wine taste.

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